

ASSET: CATEGORY EXPLAINER

SOCIAL MEDIA

Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Mostodom, YouTube, TikTok, WhatsApp, WeChat, Diyun, Didi, Weibo, LittleRedBook, Other

MAPS

Google Maps, CityMapper, Apple Maps, Paper maps, Other

MAINSTREAM MEDIA

BBC, Channel 4, New York Times, The Guardian, Podcasts, Other

DEVICES / SMART APPS

Smartphone, Smart watch, Tablet, Laptop, Other

GROUP / ASSOCIATIONS

Sports/Culture Communities, Local/Global NGOs, Student Services, Student Union, Embassies Public Organizations, Other

INFRASTRUCTURES

Transport (Bus, Tube, Bikes etc), Wifi Hotspots, CCTV, Other

SPACES

University Buildings, Student Halls, Library, Home, Places of Worship, Cultural Spaces, Leisure Centre, Green Spaces/Parks, Other

PEOPLE

Family, Friends, Co-Workers, Tutors, University Peers, Councillors/Doctors, Other

LEARNING RESOURCES

Library, Books, Journals, Google, Keats, Wikipedia, ChatGPT, Other

ACTIVITIES

Sports, Culture, Study, Leisure, Dating, Socialising, Other
